

Ayurveda and Human Resource management

The subject of Human Resource Management (HRM) plays a critical role in organizations and society at large because it addresses the management and development of peoples—the most valuable asset of any organization. The field explores how to attract, develop, retain, and maximize the potential of employees, ensuring they contribute effectively to achieving organizational goals while experiencing personal growth and satisfaction. Its significance extends far beyond administrative tasks, delving into strategic planning, workforce engagement, and ethical management.

At its core, HRM is about managing human capital in a way that aligns with an organization's strategic objectives. In today's competitive business environment, organizations rely heavily on their workforce for innovation, adaptability, and growth. Human resources are no longer just a function of hiring and firing; they are a strategic partner in achieving business success. For instance, HRM helps in aligning employee goals with company goals through performance management systems, fostering a culture of accountability and excellence.

One of the critical aspects of HRM is its focus on enhancing employee productivity and engagement. Employees perform best when they feel valued and understand how their roles contribute to the organization's success. HRM equips managers with tools to motivate employees, build trust, and create a positive work environment. It emphasizes the importance of training and development programs to upskill employees, making them more competent and future-ready. By investing in employee growth, HRM ensures that organizations have the talent they need to remain competitive in a rapidly changing world.

In an era marked by globalization and technological advancements, the role of HRM has expanded to address the complexities of managing a diverse and dispersed workforce. HR professionals are tasked with navigating challenges like cultural differences, inclusion, remote work, and rapid technological change. For example, during the shift to hybrid work models, HRM has been instrumental in creating policies that balance organizational efficiency with employee well-being.

Conflict resolution is another essential function of HRM. Disputes and misunderstandings are inevitable in any workplace, but if managed poorly, they can escalate and harm morale and productivity. HRM provides frameworks for resolving conflicts effectively, ensuring that issues are addressed constructively and relationships are preserved.

Additionally, HRM is integral to strategic planning. By forecasting workforce needs, identifying skills gaps, and planning for succession, HRM helps organizations prepare for future challenges and opportunities. It ensures that the right people are in the right roles at the right time, a crucial factor for long-term success.

The study of HRM is not just about managing people; it's about unleashing their potential and creating systems that allow both individuals and organizations to thrive. The insights gained from HRM studies are applicable across industries, making it a valuable discipline for anyone

aspiring to lead, manage, or work effectively within a team. In essence, HRM is the backbone of any organization that seeks to achieve sustainable success through its people.

Western Psychological Methods for Human Resource Management

Psychological techniques in Human Resource Management (HRM) have become essential for understanding employee behavior, improving team dynamics, and enhancing organizational performance. These methods, such as the OCEAN Model, Myers-Briggs Type Indicator (MBTI), Emotional Intelligence (EI), DISC, and psychometric testing, help HR professionals better align employees' personality traits with their roles and responsibilities.

The **OCEAN Model** (Big Five Personality Traits) evaluates five key personality dimensions—Openness, Conscientiousness, Extraversion, Agreeableness, and Neuroticism. This model is used in HRM for recruitment, team building, and personal development. It helps match individuals to roles that suit their personality, fostering better performance and job satisfaction. For example, employees with high conscientiousness are often suitable for structured, detail-oriented jobs.

The **Myers-Briggs Type Indicator (MBTI)** is another popular tool in HRM, categorizing personalities into 16 types based on preferences like Introversion vs. Extraversion and Thinking vs. Feeling. HR professionals use MBTI to improve communication, team dynamics, and leadership development by understanding how individuals process information and make decisions.

Emotional Intelligence (EI), as described by Daniel Goleman, focuses on the ability to recognize, understand, and manage emotions in oneself and others. High EI is essential for leadership, conflict resolution, and fostering a positive workplace culture. HRM uses EI assessments to identify potential leaders and improve interpersonal relationships among employees.

The **DISC Personality Profile** focuses on four behavioral traits—Dominance, Influence, Steadiness, and Conscientiousness. It helps HR professionals understand how employees interact with others, which is crucial for assigning roles, improving communication, and managing conflicts. For instance, someone with a high Dominance trait might excel in decision-making and leadership, while a person with high Steadiness would thrive in roles requiring consistency and support.

Psychometric Testing includes a range of tools that assess cognitive abilities, personality, and motivations. These tests are used to predict job performance, leadership potential, and training needs. HRM uses psychometric tools for recruitment, ensuring that candidates' abilities align with the job requirements, and for personal development programs.

Finally, **360-Degree Feedback** provides comprehensive feedback from peers, managers, and subordinates, allowing employees to gain insights into their performance from multiple perspectives. This feedback is used for leadership development and to identify areas for improvement, contributing to continuous personal and professional growth.

These psychological techniques play a vital role in optimizing the performance and well-being of employees by aligning their personal traits with their professional roles. They help organizations build stronger, more cohesive teams and ensure that employees reach their full potential. By understanding individual differences, HR professionals can make more informed decisions, leading to improved organizational outcomes and a positive workplace culture.

Introducing VAPIK Management tool for Corporate Management

All the psychological techniques used in Human Resource Management (HRM), like the OCEAN model, Myers-Briggs Type Indicator (MBTI), DISC, and other assessments, rely only on questionnaires or surveys as a primary method for collecting data. These tools are designed to capture various aspects of an individual's personality, cognitive abilities, preferences, and emotional intelligence.

Human personality is composed of four layers:

1. Natural Layer

The first layer of personality construction is the natural layer. This primarily refers to the genetic nature inherited from the parents, which is essentially the process of creation formed through the union of male and female. In Ayurveda, this is described as Vata, Pitta, and Kapha.

2. Cultural Layer

The second layer forms during the first seven to eight years of life. This is the stage where a person begins constructing their sense of self, answering the question, "Who am I?" This period leaves a lasting impression throughout their life. At this stage, the influence of the family is most prominent. It is here that a person begins identifying as Hindu, Muslim, Sikh, or Christian. The first experiences of freedom—walking and speaking—are also developed here. Additionally, impressions of wealth, poverty, language, and regional culture are formed during this stage.

3. Educational Layer

The third layer of personality develops through formal schooling. In ancient India, education was imparted in Gurukuls, where various teachers shared lifelong knowledge. Systems of thought such as Samkhya, Yoga, Mimamsa (theistic) and Charvaka, Buddhist, Jain (atheistic) philosophies were embraced. Today, students study a common curriculum until about the 10th grade, after which they specialize in a particular subject. This educational layer shapes perspectives—for instance, how a doctor views the world is different from how a plumber does. Society's behavior toward a doctor and a plumber also varies. This layer continues to expand with different dimensions of knowledge .

4. Environmental (Social) Layer

The outermost layer reflects the current circumstances in which a person lives. For example, an Indian-educated person living in Russia, the USA, or the jungles of Africa adapts their behavior to their environment. A person who throws trash anywhere in India will search for a dustbin in Singapore. Similarly, an American citizen will not behave the same way in Saudi Arabia or Afghanistan as they do in the USA. The social layer determines outward expressions like whether to wear a coat and tie or a half-jacket, or whether to put on a tilak or a cap.

Thus, human personality comprises four layers. To understand a person and elicit work from them, it is essential to understand all four layers. The social layer is the easiest to influence, while the cultural layer is the hardest to impact. Changing the natural layer is the most challenging of all.

A famous incident—though it is unclear whether it involved Birbal or Tenali Ramakrishna illustrates this concept:

A mimic once appeared in Akbar's court, capable of speaking multiple languages with such purity that it seemed each language was his native tongue. Courtiers from different regions questioned him in their native languages—be it Bhojpuri or Kannada—and the mimic responded fluently, often surpassing their proficiency. When Akbar asked his courtiers if they could determine the mimic's native language, they admitted they could not. Akbar turned to Birbal for help, and Birbal asked for a day to solve the puzzle.

The next morning, before sunrise, while the mimic was still enjoying the sweet comfort of sleep, Birbal quietly entered his room and poured cold water over his head. The mimic, startled, shouted profanities in his native tongue: “Kon pagol lok amar opor pani dhallo?” (Who is the madman who poured water on me?)

The cold water stripped away all social and environmental layers, revealing the cultural layer—his native language was Bengali.

This story highlights how stress, disasters, competition, anger, or love peel away the superficial layers of personality, exposing the deeper layers beneath.

Understanding VAPIK management

Indian System of mass management or Human Resource Management, which includes Society management and Health management is based on VAPIK system of management. VAPIK is acronym of Vat, Pitt, and Kaff, which is base of Ayurveda system of health management. Ayurveda like ancient Greeks considers humans as psychosomatic beings. The term "psychosomatic" comes from the Greek words psyche (soul), sōma (body), and nous (mind). Johann Christian August Heinroth, a German physician and professor of psychiatry, is credited with first using the term in 1818 in his book Disorders of spiritual life and their therapy.

It is important to understand that western system considers “psychosomatic system” for disease management, for which no biological reasons are found, It cares for diseases like Irritating Bowl Syndrome, migraines, High blood pressure, chronic fatigue syndrome, skin disorders etc. The

main cause of psychosomatic disease is stress or constant thinking and getting worried about something, which may or may not exist.

Indian system of VAPIK with its experience of thousands of years explores more deeper into human beings, it not only explores the diseases caused due to mind body relations but also behavior of individuals due to their basic nature at the time of conceiving the child and its birth. The modern science separates the mind from the body, so it treats body and mind differently, Body treatment is considered under allopathic system of medicine where as mind treatment is considered under psychology, even psychosomatic word is predominantly used for disease.

VAPIK system of management considers body and mind interrelated. Based on this mind is reflected through body, its type, shape and diseases. It is more scientific than the OCEAN model, Myers-Briggs Type Indicator (MBTI), DISC, and other assessments, as VAPIK not only utilizes questionnaire to find out the human psyche but it also utilizes visible behavior and body constructions and diseases related with it. In VAPIK system there are seven psychosomatic combinations they are Vata, Pitta, Kapha, Vata-Pitta, Pitta-Kapha, Kapha-Vata, Vata-Pitta-Kapha. Ayurved not only tells about their diseases but also about their personalities, which can be easily used for corporate management.

Vata	Pitt	Kaff
Charaka Samhita, Sharirasthana, 4.36: अनवस्थितचित्तोऽल्पस्मृतिर्बह्वाश्रयो भ्रमः। विभ्रमः शब्दरागश्च चेष्टान्यत्वं च वातिके॥ -Restless and have unstable thoughts -Often forgetful with a weak memory -Prone to anxiety and wandering thoughts -Drawn to sound and music -Display erratic and unpredictable behaviors	Charaka Samhita, Sharirasthana, 4.37: रोषी तीक्ष्णाभिसन्धिश्च मतिसाधुरघातकः। दृढाभिसंधः सत्ये च दीप्तां स्मृतिमधिष्ठितः॥ -Quick-tempered and prone to anger -Sharp-minded and intense in their convictions -Strategic, yet sometimes overly critical -Strong-willed and focused on truth -Possess a sharp memory	Charaka Samhita, Sharirasthana, 4.38: स्मृतिमान् धीरोपशान्तश्चिन्ताशीलः सुसंयतः। स्नेहमायाश्रयो मन्दः स्थिरो गुरुचिकीर्यकः॥ -Calm, composed, and thoughtful -Inclined toward patience and reflection -Affectionate, nurturing, and empathetic -Slow-moving but steady in action and decision-making -Possess a forgiving and generous nature

General Behavioral Traits of Doshas

Ashtanga Hridaya, Sutrasthana, 1.7:

वायुः प्राणानिलो चेतो विकारं सृजति ध्रुवम्।
पित्तं तेजः प्रकाशाय दाहाय च प्रवर्तते॥

कफः स्नेहो बलं धृत्रिर्दोषाणामेष धर्मतः ॥

- Vata governs movement and action, leading to variability in behavior.
- Pitta provides intensity, clarity, and passion but can cause irritability.
- Kapha gives stability, strength, and emotional steadiness, but may lead to inertia.

Sushruta Samhita, Sutrasthana, 21.35:

वायुः चलोऽनवस्थितः पित्तं क्रोधविवर्धनः ।

कफः स्नेहः स्थिरो ह्येवं दोषाणां स्वभावतः ॥

- Vata is inherently mobile and unstable.
- Pitta increases anger and intensity.
- Kapha is nurturing, stable, and grounded.

As we can see that based on the prakriti, one can be introduced into the works force in corporate management. Aligning the ayurvedic principle with present education system and corporate culture, following types task can be given to individual.

Vat : These predominant can be assigned with creative tasks , like research and development, Media, Movie, Music, Singing, acting, writing, website designing, etc. Vat is energy which can be directing in positive direction or negative direction. Vat dominant people can also be day dreamers, leaving the task half done, shifting the jobs frequently etc. Positive vat predominant people can be Albert Einstein, Charlie Chaplin, etc

Pitt : They are dominant in nature and good in administration, controlling the things, they can be good leaders, Pitt is predominance of fire hence they can be angry and may suffer from IBS more than others, they can also be leaders of rebel groups. Most of the leaders, those who work hard to reach the top slot in management are pitt dominant, like Narendra Modi, Valdamir Putin etc.

Kaf : They are maintainers, a quality which is required for business, long term planning”, they are calm and often emotionally more stable than the other two natures. They can be good planners and long term executors. The negative traits can be hesitant in decision making and laziness. Indian Business leaders, Ambani and Adani falls under this category.

Ayurveda deals in detail about types of prakriti and it can be great tool in achieving personal and organizational success, The Prakritis can also be used for upbringing the child so that his/her full potential can be reached, Prakriti can also play a major role in understanding the life partners and sort out the differences between them by understanding their nature.

